

The Cathodic Electrolytic Plasma Hardening of Steel and Cast Iron Based Automotive Camshafts

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Abstract. Cathodic electrolytic plasma hardening (CEPH) is a novel thermochemical surface modification and hardening process used to increase wear resistance and surface hardness of metallic components on a local area of interest. The heating efficiency is related with the plasma nozzle design, applied current and electrolyte. The nozzle design also critical factor for the hardening of complex shapes such gears and camshafts. In this work, lope of camshafts that fabricated from several cast iron and steel grades were hardened by CEPH in aqueous carbonate electrolyte using by specific plasma nozzle. The camshafts were attached on CNC lathe to turn it in horizontal axis. In order to optimise heating, the ideal flowing and wetting of electrolyte on the lope case the ellipse shape nozzle outlet ceramic was designed. As a result of preliminary studies, external surface of lobes were heated and subsequently quenched by electrolyte. The hardness of hardened surface was in the range of 50-60HRC for the different camshafts. Also no distortion was observed on the surface of lobes. Hardness depth was measured from 0.1 mm to 5 mm for the several lobes.

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1. Introduction

Surface hardening a process that includes a wide variety of techniques, is used to improve the wear resistance of parts without affecting the more soft, tough interior of the part. This combination of hard surface and resistance to breakage upon impact is useful in parts such as a cam or ring gear, bearings or shafts and automotive components that must have a very hard surface to resist wear, along with a tough interior to resist the impact that occurs during operation. Most surface treatments result in compressive residual stresses at the surface that reduce the probability of crack initiation and help arrest crack propagation at the case-core interface [1].

Cathodic electrolytic plasma hardening (CEPH) can significantly enhance the functional properties of materials, even in a very short treatment period. This technique can provide high heating rate due to the large quantity of glow discharges and hydrogen generated onto the local area of metal surface and subsequent quenching results in the formation of multi-phase mixtures of Fe₂₋₃O₄, austenite, martensite, (Fe)_xC and a nanocrystalline layer. The major advantage of the plasma electrolytic hardening is shown to be hardened layer (max. 900HV - min 500HV) of the substrates consisting of martensitic phase in very short treatment durations, approximately 7 mm thick/0.5 min. [2,3].

The more common methods currently used to harden the surface of steels include flame and induction hardening. However, each of these methods has shortcomings that can prevent its use in some applications. For example, the disadvantages of flame hardening include the possibility of part distortion, while induction hardening requires close coupling between the part and the coil (especially when using high frequencies), which must be precisely maintained [1].

Furthermore, induction hardening gives a homogenous microstructure with good wear resistance, but would be expensive to implement on a cylinder head production line due to the slow speed of the process [4]. CEPH of steel and cast iron can be achieved by localized heating and quenching, without any chemical modification of the surface. CEPH hardening also gives a homogenous hardened martensitic microstructure with good wear resistance [3].

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Camshafts are generally made of nodular cast iron, grey cast iron, chilled grey cast iron and steel. A camshaft lobes works under complicated conditions of mechanical load, and wears during operation. The contact surfaces of the cam and the follower are usually surface hardened. The hardening may be due to phase transformation or precipitation processes occurring in the material during heat treatment or thermochemical treatment [5].

CEPH process have been used to harden several ferrous materials such medium carbon steel and tool steel. Many works were performed on the flat samples. However, there is no study about the directly hardening of camshaft. Even though a wide range of materials have been studied using the CEPH, there is no published study dealing with the problem of camshaft hardening and wear resistance. The main objective of this paper is to study and experimentally (pilot scale) quantify the surface hardening of several type of original camshafts and their bearings.

2. Experimental Method

Different types of camshafts that made of nodular cast iron (NCI), gray cast iron (GCI) and C45 steel were machined and grinded to achieve final surface roughness. The photograph of camshafts was given in Figure.1.

Figure. 1. Photo of camshafts before CEPH process

CEPH was carried out on a specially designed and instrumented rig, shown in Fig. 2. This rig consist of a RPM controlled motor driver, plasma nozzle, electrolyte, electrolyte pump, PVC based electrolyte container, thermocouples, electric connection clamps, polymer based insulation bearings and DC power supply. Before the CEPH camshafts were fixed between two tailstocks. One of the tailstock is made by PTFE and another is copper. PTFE side is inserted in RPM controlled motor driver to rotate the camshafts. The copper tailstock is used to connect the cathode pincer. In this way, both camshafts were rotated and potential applied.

Figure. 2. CEPH process (a) Camshaft assembly (b) Plasma arc

An aqueous solution was prepared with 15 wt % Na_2CO_3 and di-water. The conductivity of electrolyte was 90 mS and the pH was 11. The electrolyte temperature was varied between 55-60°C. Electrolyte temperature was measured by plastic covered thermocouple probe by online measurement technique. The CEPH unit has a DC power supply; with 800V-500A power capacity, the CEPH process was performed under potential control. The camshafts were biased negatively and treated for 1.5 min for each camshaft lobe and 2 min. for bearings at the potentials varying from 250V to 400V. The electrolyte

was pumped from the container to the bottom surface of the camshaft lobes and bearings then the potential was set automatically to fix the plasma envelope. Electrolyte flow was set as 8,l/min and adjusted by valve control. To prevent the melting on the sharpen edge and corner of cam lobes, the electrolyte was directed on the cam lobe surface in a small plasma spot area which radius of plasma spot was smaller than the dimension of lobe surface. During the plasma heating the camshafts were rotated by rotating speed controlled electric motor to heat counter of cam lobes than subsequently quench. The temperature of heated cams and bearing were measured by infrared thermocouple as shown in Figure. 3.

Fig. 3. Local heating of camshaft's lobe by CEPH

Infrared temperature measurement was continuously recorded, when the all surface of bearings or lobes get 750°C the subsequently DC power switched off to cut the energy and camshafts were quenched by same electrolyte that used for heating. Also second quenching pump was used to make aggressive quenching. However, because of the different melting temperatures of steel, grey cast iron and nodular cast iron camshafts, different surface temperatures were set to prevent surface melting. For the gray and nodular cast iron the optimum surface temperature was 675°C. Experiments show that below 675°C, the hardened area was not homogenous for the circumference of lobes and bearings. For the steel, the surface temperature was 750°C. Similarly, below 750°C, the hardened area was not homogenous for the circumference of lobes and bearings.

The second problem was the not enough hardened depth. This problem was controlled by lowering the DC potential from 400V to 300V. However, reducing the DC potential causes the increasing the hardening duration from 60 sec. to 80 seconds. Another technical problem was the shape of camshaft lobes. Lobes are generally designed as asymmetric shape, consisting base circle and nose. When the heating rotating lobes, for the fixed plasma nozzle, nose part of lobe gets more energy because of plunge in to electrolyte. That's why nose parts may get heat rapidly and breaks the steady state plasma envelope. This causes the melting of edges of noses. This problem was overcome by changing the plasma nozzle system. Plasma nozzle was settled on a moving table from down to up. When the nose part of lobe goes down in the electrolyte, the moving table adjusts the gap between nozzle and nose by following the similar direction of nose route. After stabilising the heating system all camshafts' lobes and bearings were heated up to related temperature that discussed before. Later lobes and bearings were cross-sectional cut to study microstructure and measure the hardness depth and surface hardness. The hardness profiles of C45 steel, Nodular cast iron and Grey cast iron were given in Fig. 4 with related macrostructure that etched by 4% HNO₃.

The hardness depth of CEPH was evaluated by microhardness testing throughout the surface to center of lobes and base circle to interior. At low voltages such as 300V, some slight increases were measured on the near surface of the treated layer; the hardness depth was detected 1000µm beneath the surface. This is probably because of current fluctuations during the discharging and inadequate heating. As the treatment voltage increased from 350V to 400 V, depending on the increase in austenising temperature and austenited depth of samples, the microhardness and the depth of hardened zone increased. Due to high plasma discharge energy at the active surface and the very fast cooling rates. As shown in Fig. 4, max hardened layer approximately 5mm was achieved on C45 steel and nodular cast iron without any defect. On the other hand, 4mm hardened layer was achieved from grey cast iron. During heating, the heating rate at the surface of the through heated work piece is always more intense

compared to the heating rate of internal areas of the work piece and particularly, compared to the heating rate at its core. As can be seen the CEPH raised the hardness at the specimen surfaces to 650-750HV. The hardness of the untreated specimens was assumed to be uniform, at 200-250HV, throughout. Because of the cam lobe's asymmetric shape the hardness depth of peak (nose) were deeper than base circle for the all lobes. However, this type of hardened layer may bring an unique advantage. Many automotive industries prefer deeper hardness on peak side of lobe due to the wear mechanism. Considering the camshaft working conditions, one can observe that, the nose side are exposed to wear loads which may cause severe materials worn.

Fig. 4. Hardness profile of C45, NCI and GCI and their macrostructures

The normal microstructure of the GCI and NCI consists of a mixture of short graphite flakes and spheroids graphite is shown in Figure. 5. A ring of ferrite, giving the classic “bull's eye” structure, surrounds the nodular graphite. Many of the short graphite flakes are also surrounded by ferrite. The matrix primarily consists of a fine pearlite. An image from a section through the hardened surface of specimen plasma hardened to 5mm is shown in Fig. 4 and 5. The needle like structure of martensite is clearly visible. Specimen showing the martensitic structure. Also the structure consists of the same graphitic structures but both the pearlite and ferrite phases have been transformed to martensite by the plasma hardening.

Fig. 5. A section through the plasma hardened surface a 4mm, hardened specimen showing the finer martensite for the C45 steel and fine martensite around the spheres of graphite for the NCI and flake graphite for the GCI

Fig. 6 SEM micrograph of longitudinal section of the cam lobes (martensitic nose side

Figure 6 a) shows the SEM image of the martensitic microstructure of nose side of lobes made from C45 steel. The micro hardness of this martensitic zone was 675-750 HV. Figure 6 (b and c) shows the SEM image of NCI and GCI lobes that taken from fully hardened nose side. In this area, dispersed graphite spheres and graphite flakes were observed in the fine martensitic matrix. For all cams, from the plasma surface to the base metal, the hardness values decreased, and the phase structure changed into a ferritic - pearlitic matrix; in this zone hardness was measured at 30–32HRc. Dry sliding wear tests were performed using a ball on disk type wear testing. The wear tests were carried out at the sliding speed of 0.1 ms^{-1} using applied load of 30N for 100m and 500m distances. The wear test samples were taken from nose side of each testing materials. The wear results have shown that wear resistance of modified samples increased more and more times, friction coefficient was decreased (Figure. 7).

Figure 7. Wear loss and Friction Coefficient for C45, NCI and GCI specimens for different applied loads and sliding distances

It is expected that the hardened hard zone may provide a better wear resistance due to its high hardness. Figure. 7 shows the variation of wear loss with at 30 N applied normal load and 100-500m sliding distance for the treated specimen. It can be seen that the wear loss does show a remarkable difference, for NCI and GCI, but the wear resistance is much greater, compared to that of the untreated cam lobes under the same load. Wear loss shows a remarkable decrease, after plasma hardening. The best wear resistant was achieved at the NCI that was heated 60 sec and subsequently quenched. But the GCI wear resistance is lower than of the NCI, this decrease can be explained by the overheating and surface roughening. Examination of the worn surfaces revealed that under sliding against the AISI 52100 steel counterface, wear of the untreated austenitic C 45 steel occurred in a severe mode characterised by surface plastic deformation, shearing, material transfer and abrasion. Whilst the CEPH treated surfaces were worn in a mild mode characterised by micro-abrasion and surface polishing. In addition to discussed wear mechanism above, close study of the worn surfaces of the CEPH treated samples has suggested that the deformation and fatigue induced scaling of the oxide layer formed on the surface of the treated sample. Moderate adhesive /abrasive wear mechanisms also have been reported for plasma electrolytic treatment performing samples at 250V [6]. Considering the cast irons, lamellar graphitic cast structure containing long cementite with sharp tips and edges suffers from micro cracking tendency while a combination of hardness and strength of the cementite phase in the soft and ductile ferrite offers load-bearing characteristics. Graphite flakes offer lubricating characteristics in general in conditions favouring smearing of the phase on the contacting surfaces. Also, conditions allowing other micro constituents to play their positive roles like load-bearing characteristics, accommodating various phases in place and smearing causing the formation of lubricating film offer improved wear performance [7].

In order to reveal the micro cracks that originated from rapid surface heating and subsequent quenching, for the CEPH treated cam lobes, liquid penetrant testing was performed, the results show that there were no crack for the hardened surfaces. The penetrant testing experiment was shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. The penetrant testing experiment

3. Results and Discussion

Cathodic electrolytic plasma hardening (CEPH) is performed by means of electrical discharge in the plasma layer between the camshaft lobe surface and electrolytic electrode that flow from perforated hole on the lobe subsurface. The electrolyte is used for heating and cooling of the lobe surface. Cathodic electrolytic plasma hardening allows a wide variation in the heating and cooling rates (50–400°C/s) producing a treated layer from 0.1 to 10mm. A hardened layer of 6 mm case depth is formed at the surface during the treatment by carrying out plasma treatment at 675–750°C for a few minutes in a 15 wt% sodium carbonate solution. CEPH is one of the innovative technologies that have been investigated extensively in industrial levels, after optimization of electrolytic plasma technology, surface of C45 Steel, Gray CI, Nodular CI camshaft has been modified. While the value of micro-hardness of the samples was found approximately 180HV without CEPH, this value was raised up to 780HV within very short time from 30 to 120 seconds after the treatment. The hardened dept may change by heating rate and chamshaft rotating rate. The amount of macro-hardness on the surface of the samples was increased from 15HRc to approximately 60HRc. Dry sliding wear tests were performed using a ball on disk type wear testing. The wear results have shown that wear resistance of modified samples increased 5 and 6 times, for the Steel and cast iron camshafts, friction coefficient was decreased nearly two or three times. The application of CEPH proses was successfully applied for the original-industrially used automotive camshafts. Also CEPH was compared with the another common hardening technology which is called induction hardening. Comparing the induction hardening, the CEPH has some advantages such economic start-up investment cost, low cost consumables materials, controllable hardened layer depth by applying voltage and treatment duration. Also novel plasma nozzle design that controls the gap between lobe surface and electrolyte is give successful hardening process by preventing the local surface melting. The best result was achieved on the NCI samples that has unique microstructure that consist nodular graphite and hard martensitic matrix.

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